

ACTIVITY OF GOVERNMENTAL AND NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS TO PROTECT PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES IN UZBEKISTAN

Farhod Ochilov

Independent researcher at the Karshi Institute of Engineering Economics
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10394288>

Annotation: This article analyzes the activity of state and non-state organizations aimed at protecting persons with disabilities in the Republic of Uzbekistan and their legal basis.

Key words: World Organization of Health, Social, Invalidity, Obshchestvo invalidov, Mekhr-Muruvvat, Obshchestvo deaf, Veterans and molodejnye organizatsii, Fond "Nuroni".

According to the data provided by the World Health Organization, people with disabilities, which have become one of the most urgent problems in the world today, make up more than 13% of the world's population. Therefore, more than 10 laws and international documents aimed at protecting the rights and interests of persons with disabilities and creating a decent lifestyle for them have been adopted in the world today.

The Law "On social protection of disabled people in the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 18, 1991 fully complies with the requirements of the Convention, even though it was adopted a few years before the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. Especially in 2008, as a result of the adoption of a new version of this law, the personal, political, and economic rights of disabled people, like all healthy people, were guaranteed, and broad democratic rights and freedoms were established for disabled people in all aspects of social life. In 2009, the Republic of Uzbekistan signed the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. This indicates that the legislative system of protection of the disabled in accordance with world standards is being formed in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Because the Law "On social protection of disabled people in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and all articles of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan correspond to the requirements of the "Convention on the Rights of the Disabled" and the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights". The requirements of the convention reflect aspects of the social model of attitude towards disabled people. But the mechanism of its implementation was not fully developed.

This decree was adopted on the basis of a complete analysis of the state of social protection and support of the disabled by the commission for the preparation of proposals aimed at the fundamental improvement of the system

of support for persons with disabilities. This has made a radical change in terms of raising the quality of life of persons with disabilities to another level and fully ensuring their rights in all aspects. According to this decree, the term "disabled person" was introduced instead of the term "disabled". Now this term is widely used in the normative documents being developed in Uzbekistan. It should be noted here that the term "disabled" is actually a concept specific to the medical model. In the social model, the term "disabled person" or "person with a disability" is widely used, not "disabled". Although the concept of social model is still widely used in the world today, the term "disabled" is widely used in international legal documents. For example, we can cite concepts such as "Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" or "Declaration on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities", "International Day of Persons with Disabilities". It would be appropriate if the society of disabled people in Uzbekistan was called "Society of Persons with Disabilities" or "Society of Persons with Limited Opportunities".

As defined in the Convention, the Law "On Social Protection of Disabled Persons in Uzbekistan" states that they have the right to join non-governmental non-commercial organizations that serve the interests of disabled persons in order to ensure equal opportunities with all other citizens in the exercise of their rights and freedoms, and to create conditions for a fulfilling lifestyle¹.

On the basis of this, the legal and organizational foundations of democratic institutions, which are the basis of civil society in our country, are fully formed, and the reforms in the processes of their development are deepening more and more. It is known that there were about 100 non-governmental non-commercial organizations in our country on the eve of independence, and today their number has reached 9 thousand. (1 diagram). Among them, more than 78 serve the special interests of the disabled and can be divided into the following types:

1. Associations. National Paralympic Association of Uzbekistan, Association of NGOs of Uzbekistan, Association of Disabled Businesswomen of Uzbekistan, Association for Osteoporosis.

2. Societies. Uzbekistan Red Crescent Society, Uzbekistan Blind Society, Uzbekistan Deaf Society.

3. Funds. Social support for veterans of Uzbekistan "Nuroni" Foundation, "PanoH Shulsi" public fund for rehabilitation of blind and weak children and youth of Uzbekistan, "You are not alone" Republican public children's fund, "Vatan" of disabled veterans of armed conflicts and anti-terrorist struggle of

¹ The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On social protection of disabled people in the Republic of Uzbekistan"// Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2013. No. 18. Article 233.

Uzbekistan charity fund, vocational colleges, talent funds of low-income families studying in academic lyceums and financial support for disabled children, "Mehr-muruvvat" public fund, anemia and leukemia public fund, supporting non-governmental non-profit organizations under the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other institutions of civil society - support community fund.

1. Centers. Center for the Study of Human Rights and Humanitarian Rights, Republican Center for Social Adaptation of Children.

2. Associations. National Breast Cancer Association for Life

3. Federations. Powerlifting Association of Uzbekistan, Blind Sports Federation of Uzbekistan, Deaf Sports Federation of Uzbekistan.

Non-governmental non-profit organizations report continuously to the Directorate of Public, Non-Governmental and Religious Organizations of the Ministry of Justice and have their own management structure. The Society of the Disabled of Uzbekistan, the Society of the Blind of Uzbekistan, the Society of the Deaf form the main link among them and operate independently of each other, they have branches in regions, cities and districts.

Among these Non-Governmental and Religious Organizations, the Deaf and Blind Society of Uzbekistan has many years of history and experience. The Deaf Society was founded in 1929, and the Blind Society was founded in 1932. The main goal of the societies is to unite blind, deaf and hard-of-hearing persons, to protect them and to help them realize their civil, economic, social and cultural rights, to ensure their social rehabilitation and integration into modern society². The Deaf Society of Uzbekistan has built 19 enterprises for deaf and dumb disabled people, 2 republic health rehabilitation centers, a sports complex, a stadium, and a boarding house "Zilol" for recreation in the Jizzakh region.³

On March 19, 1992, the Republican Association "Chernobyl Chilar of Uzbekistan" was established in accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on unification of regional public organizations and coordination of activities of the "Chernobyl" association. The Association of Chernobyl Victims performs the tasks of providing practical assistance to citizens who suffered losses in the Chernobyl disaster and other radiation-nuclear facilities, as well as to families and children who died, and to organize a network of pharmacies to supply Chernobyl victims with drugs for free at the expense of the association⁴. In 2000, the number of its members

² O'zbekiston karlar jamiyati nizomi. 1991 yil 14 mart.

³ O'zbekistonda nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlar to'g'risida ma'lumotnoma. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, – B. 125.

⁴ O'zbekistonda nogironlar jamiyatlari to'g'risidagi ma'lumotnoma. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2000. – B. 48.

reached 10,000, and it is a member of the international "Soyuz Chernobyl". (It includes America, Asia, Australia and European countries)⁵. In addition, the Association of Disabled Women Entrepreneurs of Uzbekistan, the Association of Disabled Entrepreneurs "Nur", the Disabled People's Society of Uzbekistan, "Status", "Kindness", "Umidvorlik", "Sisters", "Millennium", "Mehr Kozda", which are effectively operating in our Republic. we can cite non-governmental non-profit organizations as an example. But these NGOs mainly operate in the central and few regions of the republic. Branches of the Association of Disabled Women Entrepreneurs of Uzbekistan exist mainly in Samaraqand, Bukhara and Namangan regions, and many disabled women in the remaining regions feel the need to unite in order to conduct business activities. They operate only in the name of branches of other types of NGOs.

The societies cooperate with other associations and organizations in the republic and abroad in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on public associations, "On non-governmental non-profit organizations", "On social protection of the disabled", applicable legislation and their own charter. In addition, NGOs cooperate with various state organizations, that is, they act as mediators between people with disabilities and state organizations. At this point, the cooperative activities of the society of disabled people can be divided into 3 directions:

1. Cooperation with republican non-governmental non-commercial organizations.
2. Cooperation with state organizations.
3. Cooperation with foreign and international NGOs, international charity organizations.

International cooperation with the United Nations Development Program, Japan's International Cooperation Agency (JICA), South Korea's International Charity Agency (KOIKA) is an example.

In our country, the members of the society of disabled people cooperated with the structures of state power and management through the People's Democratic Party. They actively participate in the political life of the country and nominate their representatives to local authorities. For example, a memorandum of cooperation was signed between the Society of Disabled People of Uzbekistan and the People's Democratic Party. "Mehribonlik" mutual social assistance center for the disabled signed a memorandum of cooperation with the "Milliy

Tikalnish" democratic party, and "Status" legal assistance center for the disabled with the Social Democratic Party of Justice. For example, in 2004, 14 out of 30 candidates became deputies, and in 2009, 9 of such candidates were elected deputies to local state bodies⁶. The disabled society has been cooperating with the People's Democratic Party for almost 20 years.

It operates within the interests of the disabled in cooperation with state organizations, mainly the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Health, and local authorities. From the first years of independence, the ministries of social welfare of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan, departments in regions, cities formed a single system of the social welfare body of the republic⁷. The Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population is considered to be the state management body in Uzbekistan for ensuring the unified state policy in the field of social protection of persons with disabilities. According to Karimov's decree of February 22, 2016 "On organizational measures to further improve the system of medical social assistance to the needy segments of the population" and the decision of February 24, 2016 "On measures to improve the organization of the Ministry of Labor of the Republic of Uzbekistan", disabled people, war veterans, veterans, providing medical and social assistance to lonely elderly people and other vulnerable segments of the population, as well as issues of their education and professional training were assigned to the Ministry of Health.

Control over determining and paying social benefits and material support for the disabled and other needy strata of the population will be carried out by the Ministry of Finance. "Muruvat" and "Sakhavat" houses, national center for rehabilitation and prosthetics of the disabled, regional rehabilitation centers for the disabled, sanatoriums and boarding houses for war and labor veterans, specialized vocational colleges for the disabled in Tashkent and Ferghana, labor and social protection of the population (It was transferred from the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations to the Ministry of Health. This directly serves to rehabilitate disabled persons, effectively organize the activities of medical and social service institutions for them, and raise their quality of life to another level.

In the Ministry of Health and Finance, a comprehensive system of social protection of the disabled, their rehabilitation and ensuring their employment has been formed. Today, the system of the Ministry of Health has 33 "Sahavat"

⁶ Deputy Chairman of the Disabled People's Society of Uzbekistan O. Interview with Isakov. Report of the Society of Disabled Persons of Uzbekistan on the results of 2014.

⁷ Usmonova M.A. O'zbekistonda keksalar va nogironlarni himoya qilishning tashkiliy-huquqiy asoslari: Yurid. fan. nom. diss... – Toshkent, 1995. – B. 72.

and "Muruvat" houses, 7 sanatoriums and recreation centers, 11 national centers for medical, social and occupational rehabilitation of the disabled.⁸ Departments, branches and departments for the provision of medical and social assistance to the disabled and other needy segments of the population were established under the Ministry of Health. Directly based on their authority, they help to send disabled people in need of medical and social assistance, including children with disabilities and lonely elderly people to "Muruvvat" and "Sakhavat" boarding schools, rehabilitation centers for disabled people and sanatoriums for war and labor veterans, citizens themselves Together with the management bodies, it carries out the tasks of organizing social services based on an individual program that takes into account the care of other people and single elderly citizens who need help at home, to select and provide suitable types of medical and social assistance to the disabled. Therefore, the cooperative activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations and state organizations form a system of social protection for the disabled.

The amount of funds to be allocated from the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and state special funds to support the activities of NGOs is approved annually as a separate item in the main parameters of the State budget expenditures of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the proposal of the Parliamentary Commission. From the establishment of the public fund until 2013, about 30 billion soums were allocated to this fund from the state budget. More than 1 billion 614 million soums of these funds are directed to the support of regional and district associations of the disabled people of Uzbekistan, disabled people's societies, and different age groups of the population with limited physical abilities. During these years, the number of supported projects increased by 2.1 times, the amount of allocated funds increased by 3.6 times.

List of used sources and references:

1. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On social protection of the disabled in the Republic of Uzbekistan" // Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2013. No. 18. Article 233. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2015. - B. 15.
2. National archive of Uzbekistan, collection M.37, list 1, collective volume 5437. Page 285.
3. National archive of Uzbekistan, collection M.37, list 1, volume 5437. Page 177.
4. Meliyev X. Fuqarolik jamiyatini shakllantirishning milliy modeli / Qadriyat. – Toshkent, 2013 yil 28 dekabr. – B. 2.

⁸ Hajabov I. Imtiyozli yo'llanmalar kimlarga beriladi? // Bir safda. – Toshkent, 2013. – №3. – B. 12.

5. Rajabov I. Imtiyozli yo‘llanmalar kimlarga beriladi? // Bir safda. – Toshkent, 2013. – №3. – B. 12

